

Studies in the Synthesis of Furocoumarins : Part (XXIV)* Synthesis of Difurocoumarin Derivatives

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4-Hydroxy-7-allyloxycoumarin(Ia), on allylation and Claisen rearrangement gave 7-allyloxy-2-methyl-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran(IIa) and 7-hydroxy-6-allyl-2-methyl-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran(IIb). (IIa), on further Claisen rearrangement gave (IIb) which on cyclisation followed by dehydrogenation afforded 2,7-dimethyl-4-oxo-4H-difuro(3,2-c : 2',3'-h)benzopyran(IV). 2,6,8-Trimethyl-4-oxo-4H-difuro(3,2-c : 3',2'-g)benzopyran(V) and 2,9-dimethyl-4-oxo-4H-difuro(3,2-c : 3',2'-f)benzopyran(VII) were similarly synthesised from 4-hydroxy-7-allyloxy-8-methylcoumarin(Ic) and 4-hydroxy-6-allyloxy-8-methylcoumarin(Ie) respectively.

CLAISEN migration of diallyloxy-4-phenylcoumarin derivatives is rarely reported in the literature. Seshadri and coworkers¹ have studied the Claisen migration of 5,7-diallyloxy-4-phenylcoumarin and obtained the bis-2'-methyl-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo-[4',5' : 5,6 and 4',5' : 7,8]-4-phenylcoumarin and 2'-methyl-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo-[4',5' : 7,8]-5-hydroxy-6-allyl-4-phenylcoumarin. It was therefore, thought of interest to study the Claisen migration of diallyloxy-4-phenylcoumarins and to synthesise difurocoumarins for the evaluation of their psoralene like photosensitizing activity.

We report here the syntheses of 2,7-dimethyl-4-oxo-4H-difuro (3,2-c : 2',3'-h)benzopyran(IV), 2,6,8-trimethyl-4-oxo-4H-difuro (3,2-c : 3',2'-g)benzopyran(V) and 2,9-dimethyl-4-oxo-4H-difuro (3,2-c : 3',2'-f) benzopyran(VII).

4-Hydroxy-7-allyloxy-8-methylcoumarin^a(Ia), on allylation with allylbromide gave 4,7-diallyloxy-8-methylcoumarin(Ib). Claisen rearrangement of 4,7-diallyloxy-8-methylcoumarin gave two products as shown by TLC which were identified as 7-allyloxy-2-methyl-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran(IIa) and 7-hydroxy-6-allyl-2-methyl-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c) benzopyran(IIb). (IIb) was also obtained on further migration of (IIa). The structure of (IIa) was confirmed by its NMR spectrum (CDCl₃): δ -1.58, doublet, (3H, -CH₃ at position-2, J=7Hz), 3.60, multiplet (2H, -CH₂ at position-3, J=7Hz), 4.55, doublet, (2H, Ar-O-CH₂-CH=CH₂, J=5Hz), 5.2, multiplet, (1H at position-2), 5.45, doublet, (2H, Ar-O-CH₂-CH=CH₂), 5.9-6.2, multiplet, (1H Ar-O-CH₂-CH=CH₂, J=5Hz), 6.8-7.6, multiplet (3H, aromatic protons at position-6, -8 and -9). Compound (IIb), on cyclisation with conc. sulphuric acid gave 2,7-dimethyl-4-oxo-4H-2,3,6,7-tetrahydrodifuro(3,2-c : 2',3'-h)benzopyran(III). The structure of (III) was confirmed by its NMR spectrum (CDCl₃): δ -1.5,

doublet, (3H, -CH₃ group at position-7), 1.62 doublet, (3H, -CH₃ group at position-2), 2.5-3.5, multiplet (4H, two cyclic methylene groups at position-3 and -6), 4.9-5.4 multiplet (2H, two cyclic methine protons at position-2 and -7), 6.8 doublet, (1H aromatic proton at position -9, J=8Hz), 7.5 doublet (aromatic proton at position-10, J=8Hz). Dehydrogenation of (III) by palladised charcoal (10%) gave 2,7-dimethyl-4-oxo-4H-difuro(3,2-c : 2',3'-h)benzopyran(IV).

4-Hydroxy-7-allyloxy-8-methylcoumarin(Ic) on similar series of reaction afforded 2,6,8-trimethyl-4-oxo-4H-difuro(3,2-c : 3',2'-g)benzopyran(V).

4-Hydroxy-6-allyloxy-8-methylcoumarin(Ie), on allylation with allylbromide and anhydrous potassium carbonate in dry acetone gave 4,6-diallyloxy-8-methylcoumarin(I f). Claisen rearrangement of (I f) gave alkali soluble product, 8-hydroxy-9-allyl-2-methyl-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c) benzopyran(II d), which on cyclisation with conc. sulphuric acid afforded 2,9-dimethyl-2,3,9-10-tetrahydro-4-oxo-4H-difuro(3,2-c : 3',2'-f)benzopyran(VI) the structure of which was confirmed by its NMR spectrum (CDCl₃): δ -1.46-1.61, triplet, overlapping two doublets, (6H, two -CH₃ groups at position-2 and -9, J=7Hz), 2.6-2.8, multiplet (4H, two cyclic methylene groups at positions -3 and -10, overlapping each other), 4.85-5.38, multiplet, (2H, two methine protons at position -2 and -9 overlapping each other), 6.9 doublet (1H, aromatic proton at position-7, J=9Hz), 7.15, doublet, (1H, aromatic proton at position-6, J=9Hz). Dehydrogenation of (VI) by palladised charcoal gave 2,9-dimethyl-4-oxo-4H-difuro(3,2-c : 3',2'-f)benzopyran(VII).

Experimental

IR spectra (nujol) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 457 and Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer.

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- (Ia) R=OH, R₁=R₂=R₄=H, R₃=-OCH₂CH=CH₂,
 (Ib) R=R₂=-OCH₂CH=CH₂, R₁=R₃=R₄=H
 (Ic) R=OH, R₁=R₂=H, R₃=-OCH₂CH=CH₂, R₄=-CH₃,
 (Id) R=R₂=-OCH₂CH=CH₂, R₁=R₃=H, R₄=-CH₃,
 (Ie) R=-OH, R₁=R₃=R₄=H, R₂=-OCH₂CH=CH₂,
 (If) R=R₂=-OCH₂CH=CH₂, R₁=R₃=R₄=H

- (IIa) R₁=R₂=R₄=H, R₃=-OCH₂CH=CH₂,
 (IIb) R₁=R₂=H, R₃=-OH, R₄=-CH₂CH=CH₂,
 (IIc) R₁=H, R₂=-OCH₂CH=CH₂, R₃=-OH, R₄=-CH₃,
 (IId) R₁=-CH₂CH=CH₂, R₂=-OH, R₃=R₄=H

meters, NMR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer R-32 NMR spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. The UV absorption spectra were recorded on Beckmann DU-spectrophotometer. All the compounds exhibited expected C,H analyses.

4,7-Diallyloxycoumarin(Ib)

4-Hydroxy-7-allyloxycoumarin was prepared according to Dholakia and Trivedi².

A mixture of 4-Hydroxy-7-allyloxycoumarin (5 g), allylbromide (3 g) and anhy. potassium carbonate (10 g) was boiled under reflux for 8 hr. in dry

acetone (200 ml) on a water bath. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual. The product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 94°. Yield 2.5 g.

4,7-Diallyloxy-8-methylcoumarin(Id), m.p. 156° and 4,6-diallyloxycoumarin(If), m.p. 119° were prepared according to the above method from 4-hydroxy-7-allyloxy-8-methylcoumarin²(Ic), and 4-hydroxy-6-allyloxycoumarin²(Ie) respectively.

7-Hydroxy-6-allyl-2-methyl-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)-benzopyran(IIb) :

4,7-Diallyloxycoumarin (2 g) was refluxed with dimethylaniline (10 ml) for 8 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into conc. hydrochloric acid containing crushed ice. The reaction mixture was extracted with ether and the ethereal layer was shaken with sodium hydroxide solution. The alkaline layer was separated and acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid. The separated product was filtered and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 222°. Yield 1.5g.

The ether extract after the removal of the solvent gave little amount of the compound 7-allyloxy-2-methyl-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran (IIa). IR spectra 1710 cm⁻¹ (lactonyl>C=O group), 1275 cm⁻¹ (aromatic ether linkage), 875 cm⁻¹ (furan ring).

Compound (IIc), m.p. 179° and (IId), m.p. 255° were prepared from (Id) and (If) respectively according to the method described above.

Claisen rearrangement of 4-allyloxy-2-methyl-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran(IIa) :

(IIa) (0.5 g) was refluxed with dimethylaniline (5 ml) for 8 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as before and the product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 222°. Yield 0.3 g. The mixed m.p. with (IIb) was not depressed.

2,7-Dimethyl-4-oxo-4H-2,3,6,7-Tetrahydrodifuro(3,2-c : 2',3'-h)-benzopyran (III) :

7-Hydroxy-6-allyl-2-methyl-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo-(3,2-c)benzopyran (IIb), (1 g) was triturated with conc. sulphuric acid (5 ml) for 15 min. at room temperature. The mixture was poured into crushed ice. The separated product was filtered and washed with sodium hydroxide solution to remove unreacted compound. The compound was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 147°. Yield 0.8 g. IR spectrum (nujol) 1720 cm⁻¹ (lactonyl>C=O group), 840 cm⁻¹ and 905 cm⁻¹ (two furan rings).

This method was employed to 7-hydroxy-8-allyl-2,6-dimethyl-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran(IIc) and 8-hydroxy-9-allyl-2-methyl-2,3-

dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran(II_d) to give 2, 6, 8-trimethyl-4-oxo-4H-2, 3, 8, 9-tetrahydrodifuro(3,2-c : 3',2'-g) benzopyran, m.p. 167°. IR spectrum 1690 cm⁻¹ (lactonyl>C=O group), 830 cm⁻¹ and 890 cm⁻¹ (two furan rings); $\lambda_{\text{Max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 246 nm (log e 4.07), 294 (log e 3.93), 324 nm (log e 4.33), 338 nm (log e 4.29); and 2,9-dimethyl-2,3,10-tetrahydro-4-oxo-4H-difuro(3,2-c : 3',2'-f) benzopyran(VI), m.p. 180°, $\lambda_{\text{Max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 269 nm (log e 4.13), 307 nm (log e 4.05), 342 nm (log e 3.63), respectively.

2,7-Dimethyl-4-oxo-4H-difuro(3,2-c : 2',3'-h)benzopyran (IV) :

A mixture of 2,7-dimethyl-4-oxo-4H-2,3,6,7-tetrahydrodifuro(3,2-c : 2',3'-h)benzopyran (0.5g), palladised charcoal (0.3g, : 10%) was refluxed with diphenyl ether (4 ml) for 12 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot. After cooling petroleum ether was added to the filtrate. The separated product was filtered and washed with petroleum ether several times. The product crystallised from benzene, m.p. 225°. Yield 0.3g. (Found : C, 71.06; H, 3.76. C₁₈H₁₀O₄ requires : C, 70.89; H, 3.93%). IR spectrum (Nujol) 1730 cm⁻¹ (lactonyl>C=O group), 800 cm⁻¹ and 880 cm⁻¹ (two furan rings), $\lambda_{\text{Max}}^{\text{CHCl}_3}$ 255 nm (log e 4.50), 268 nm (log e 4.41), 305 nm (log e 4.19), 320 nm (log e 4.12), 330 nm (log e 4.05), 336 nm (log e 4.01).

Compound (V), m.p. 218°, (Found : C, 71.68; H, 4.72. C₁₈H₁₀O₄ requires : C, 71.65; H, 4.48%), IR spectrum Nujol 1715 cm⁻¹ (lactonyl>C=O group). 825 cm⁻¹ (two furan rings), $\lambda_{\text{Max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 304 nm (log e 4.09), 332 nm (log e 4.19); and (VII), m.p. 228° (Found : C, 70.87; H, 3.60. C₁₈H₁₀O₄ requires : C, 70.88; H, 3.94%).

$\lambda_{\text{Max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 326 nm (log e 4.50), 342 nm (log e 4.41) were prepared from 2,6,8-trimethyl-4-oxo-4H-2,3,8,9-tetrahydrodifuro(3,2-c : 3',2'-g)benzopyran and (VI) respectively, according the method described above.

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